
Pipeline for AI-generated News Detection

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Abstract The widespread adoption of Large Language Models (LLMs) has introduced new challenges related to misinformation management and content traceability, leading to the proliferation of “careless speech.” Contemporary journalism faces significant risks due to the rapid spread of AI-generated. A critical application in this scenario is the continuous detection of text generated by artificial intelligence, due to the potential lack of transparency. This work proposes a pipeline for continuous AI-made news detection based on LLM fine-tuning. This is then evaluated in a use case tailored to the Brazilian news ecosystem, as a proof of concept. This work formalizes a replicable process, defining a data acquisition step, input generation and text classification through LLM fine-tuning. The case results in two distinct fine-tuning stages of different models, along with a comparison of the application of traditional machine learning approaches for embedding classification. Results demonstrate strong classification performance, particularly from fine-tuned BERT models. The proposed process could also be expanded and incorporated into the text curation process in media organizations or embedded into social networks.

Keywords: Large Language Models, Fine-Tuning, Artificial Intelligence, Modern Journalism, PEFT, QLoRA

1 Introduction

As commercial and personal use of Large Language Models (LLMs) becomes more widespread and commodified, several secondary problems arise from software misuse. In the past, information could not be disseminated within seconds, let alone generated automatically. Today, however, identifying sources and verifying the reliability of online information has become an increasingly complex challenge, especially in the context of contemporary journalism, which is often affected by conflicts of interest and weaponized fake news distribution.

As described in a report by the Reuters Institute [Adami, 2024], inappropriate content generated by AI brings a new dynamic to the regulation of fake news, reporting the use of AI to generate mass content with the aim of manipulating public opinion or simply generating profit through the common embedded advertising system [Buzz, 2015]. The result of this dynamic is the dissemination of content without traceability of responsibility and without the slightest commitment to the proper ethics involved in journalistic writing. This is referred to as AI-made “*careless speech*” [Wachter *et al.*, 2024], textual content that may satisfy a user’s interest, but has no commitment to the truth. Consequently, there is a new dynamic in this modern environment of information dissemination between independent agents, that of lack of liability and management of information generated by LLM misuse.

Another concept addressed by Adami [2024] is the idea of recursion in the content generated by LLM in its training. Content that is easy to create and of low quality, as it proliferates on the Internet, constitutes a risk as it becomes the input of a new model, affecting the results of other LLMs to come. There is a need to understand what is original or human-curated content and what is automated content, specializing existing products [Copyleaks, 2025].

So, how can this issue be approached in a way that increases transparency in the user journey when consuming

third-party content? The proposal of this work focuses on recognizing architectural limitations and mapping related proposals to serve as input for a pipeline proposal based on LLM fine-tuning. This pipeline is then applied using the reality of Brazilian journalism as a case study for validation. The main steps of the pipeline are to retrieve text specific to the Brazilian news domain (in Portuguese), generate enriched domain-specific text, and classify it by fine-tuning well established LLMs.

The result of this experiment is therefore intended to support a user’s journey to identify whether content from an unknown source is generated by misuse, or potentially malicious, use of AI. Consequently, serving as a flagging system with the potential to be later turned into a product. It is understood that there is great difficulty in validating the veracity of news in an automated and unbiased way (as it will be further explained in the Section 2). However, the focus of an AI-generated news classifier, news that can be configured as potentially of lower quality, can prove to be an effective tool when preprocessing information by asking a user to be aware of the origin of the information that is being consumed.

This work is presented through the consolidation of related works (Section 2), presentation of the methodology used (Section 3), theoretical basis tailored to LLM fine-tuning (Section 4), the Architecture of the proposed Pipeline (Section 5) and presentation of a case study to validate the proposed for news identification in the Brazilian context (Section 6). Finally, a Conclusion and future works (Section 7) are discussed.

2 Related Work

Üyük *et al.* [2024] introduced a framework proposal by generating and classifying strings in the context of AI-generated news. However, the focus of this paper does not include a formalization of a continuous pipeline that includes the acquisition of an intermediate model and a final classi-

fier model (although these steps have been presented). Üyük *et al.* [2024] introduces a comparison between approaches (models with fine-tuning and models in a zero-shot classification approach) and has one of its differentials in demonstrating a classification comparison using LLM prompt engineering.

Kumarage *et al.* [2023] proposes a framework for AI-generated news detection, also using language models such as OpenAI's GPT [OpenAI *et al.*, 2024]. Kumarage *et al.* [2023] differentiates itself by presenting an adversarial approach between a classifier and a generator model, integrating into the test suite an approach based on perturbing the input of the classifier to determine the robustness. Success cases are demonstrated for generative models based on GPT 3.5 for example. Ding *et al.* [2023] addressed the impact caused by the use of LLMs specifically to generate news headlines, and their methods also consisted on the systematic use of human intervention to determine satisfaction with the result obtained.

Other related studies (such as Guo *et al.* [2024] and Chen *et al.* [2023]) demonstrate approaches to detect AI-generated text from specific models. In other words, it does not represent a proposed response to the detection of text generated by multiple sources.

Even given their strong results, none of these studies examine their effectiveness in the context of Portuguese-language journalism (Üyük *et al.* [2024], for example, concentrates efforts on English, Turkish, Hungarian, and Persian languages). Üyük *et al.* [2024] also does not elaborate on the potential use of fine-tuning optimization methodologies such as QLora [Dettmers *et al.*, 2023], and the application of Retrieval-Augmented Generation methods. The work shown in Chen *et al.* [2023] focuses on the detection of only text generated by GPT, but as will be elaborated later in this work, detecting only text generated by a specific model does not fit the use case proposed to detect AI-generated news. Kumarage *et al.* [2023] and similar proposals differ from the pipeline approach proposed in the present work by integrating different generators and different classifiers for continuous retraining.

Models analogous to the classification model presented in the case study in our work were also not found in Hugging Face [Hugging Face, 2025b], which serves as an open platform for sharing Large Language Models and related models.

In the context of the case study for the pipeline validation, LLMs for specific domains in the Portuguese language were also found. However, none of the models satisfies the use case of the vocabulary of Brazilian newsrooms. Models with good results were found in the context of Biology, such as BioBERTpt [Schneider *et al.*, 2020] and GPT2-BioPt [Schneider *et al.*, 2021]. In the banking domain, BERTau [Finardi *et al.*, 2021] obtained satisfactory results, in addition to LegalBert-pt [Silveira *et al.*, 2023] and BERTikal [Polo *et al.*, 2021] for the legal domain. Generalist models can be applied, such as Bertimbau [Souza *et al.*, 2020], Sabiá [Pires *et al.*, 2023a], GPorTuguese-2 [Guillou, 2020] and PTT5 [Carmo *et al.*, 2020].

Therefore, the main contributions of this work are:

- To propose a text classification pipeline for AI-

generated news based on the reuse of well established Large Language Models, with the use of enriched LLM-made text as an intermediate step. Hardware-optimized LLM fine-tuning (Section 4.2) and basis for continuous development guided by well-defined steps.

- To address a specialization of an existing product in a generalist context: to identify AI-generated news in an automated and bias-free manner using news written in Brazilian Portuguese as a use case for validation, serving as an example for an update to other text classifiers that do not satisfy this specific use.

2.1 Traditional News Fact Checking

To begin the development process itself, it is necessary to contextualize the business understanding in which this project is inserted: the scenario of modern journalism and media consumption, with a focus on the Brazilian context.

The validation of fake news is widely spread in the Brazilian media [CNJ, 2024], being a point of great concern for the general public. The usual fact checking process is based on two different, but complementary, methodologies.

Firstly and most traditionally [CNJ, 2025], the manual validation through investigative journalistic writing (e.g. Estadão Verifica [Estadão, 2025], UOL Confere [UOL, 2025]). This process is overseen by a designated journalistic editorial team. However, it is a manual work that consumes a large amount of time and resources, validating only news chosen according to the internal criteria of each institution (for example, popularity of a news article or if an article is judged to be particularly harmful). This overhead in validation becomes a problem in modern journalism, as the speed at which information is disseminated is higher than ever.

Complementing traditional approaches, there are validators built into social networks that are based on user annotations. One example of greater notoriety is the X (formerly Twitter) flagging system known as “Community Notes” [X, 2025]. As a post gains traction, users of the network organically have the possibility of reporting information in a given post that is deemed as being false.

In the context of “careless speech” and automated mass content creation, there is a clear limitation in assuming that most text generated by AI is automatically incorrect or serves malicious purposes. In contrast, an AI-generated content flagging system has the potential to be an automated preprocessing for existing systems. The basic premise is that dubious content that presents itself transparently as AI-generated content to a user requires further validation, implying a lack of credibility in the information. This premise is entirely based on data transparency between users and has the ability to reduce the impact of the use of AI to manipulate public opinion on a larger scale.

3 Methodology

This work is based on the application of Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) [Wirth and Hipp, 2000] as illustrated in Figure 1. The CRISP-DM process is

Figure 1. Macro view of the applied process, based on CRISP-DM.

widely used due to its flexibility and applicability in different contexts, outlining the work to be done in clear steps and continuation criteria.

Applied to the objective of this article and the context of modern journalism, the following tasks are performed in each mapped stage of CRISP-DM:

- **Business Understanding:** There are well-known AI-generated text identifiers [Chaka, 2023] and traditional Brazilian fact checkers [CNJ, 2025], but there is a gap between the two products that could be successfully treated with an automated preprocessing step, a careless speech identifier. There is also the potential to not just develop a model but a methodology for continuous development through a pipeline. This is shown in Section 2.
- **Data Understanding:** mapping the desired dataset profile (obtained by web scraping) aligned with the Brazilian journalistic writing domain and defining how to perform fine-tuning of LLMs. Questions to be answered at this stage include the ideal amount of real news, target size of strings to be generated given the average of human-made news articles, and mapping of the process of normalizing strings originated from the data collection process. This is the direct prerequisite of Section 5.
- **Data Preparation and Modeling:** Consolidation of datasets for different substages of the pipeline and structuring of models to be used. Consolidated through Section 5 and briefly contextualized through Section 4.
- **Evaluation:** Objective comparison of results of the final classifier model and plausibility assessment of strings generated by the intermediate generator model. Consolidated through Section 6.
- **Deploy:** This step shows how the proposed pipeline can be integrated with existing products [Chaka, 2023]. It is illustrated through a use case in Section 6 and further discussed in Section 7, highlighting its practical deployment and context.

4 Theoretical Foundation

In this section, a general context is presented for language models and paradigms of greatest relevance to the result of the specific application presented in this article. The architecture of Transformers and Self-Attention Mechanisms [Vaswani *et al.*, 2023] are briefly contextualized, and training steps and effective usage of different models will be covered in greater depth to provide a basis for the results obtained in this article in Section 6, in addition to differentiating the use of two different types of models (BERT [Devlin *et al.*, 2019a] and models like Llama [Grattafiori *et al.*, 2024] and GPT [OpenAI *et al.*, 2024] for synthetic string generation). The way in which fine-tuning occurs in the final version of the pipeline using QLora [Dettrmers *et al.*, 2023] is presented in Section 6.

4.1 Large Language Models

Large Language Models (LLMs) usually refer to neural networks based upon the Transformer architecture built on self-attention mechanisms [Zhao *et al.*, 2024]. LLMs are considered to be the latest iteration on language models research given the wide perspective on problem solving as previous iterations. For a long time, the now what are considered to be smaller models, have been efficient in NLP tasks (such as numerical representation of strings) and to improve performance in information retrieval systems. Similarly, as more complex models gained prominence, the use of multi-layer perceptrons (MLPs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to compute word sequence probabilities became a key focus in the research community [Prince, 2023].

Early attempts at capturing meaningful word representations emerged as quite effective, as word2vec [Mikolov *et al.*, 2013] proved to be very efficient in NLP tasks. This attempt proposed to build a simplified shallow neural network, which further increased interest in developing networks of higher complexity. This consolidated not only the research paradigm in computing the probability of words in a sequence, but also in the numerical representation of strings in the most efficient way possible, which is known as textual embeddings tasks.

The Transformer architecture with self-attention enabled the development of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [Devlin *et al.*, 2019b], a milestone in language modeling. Pre-trained on large unlabeled datasets, BERT introduced context-aware word representations, significantly enhancing semantic analysis capabilities over previous non-pre-trained methods such as word2vec [Mikolov *et al.*, 2013] and TF-IDF [Sammur and Webb, 2010].

More advanced models like Llama [Grattafiori *et al.*, 2024] and GPT [OpenAI *et al.*, 2024] use Causal Language Modeling (CLM) during pre-training to predict the next token. These models rely on the Transformer architecture and serve both as encoders and decoders, performing tasks from text embedding to synthetic text generation [Radford *et al.*, 2019]. They are foundational for chatbot products (e.g., ChatGPT, Microsoft Copilot) and advanced multimodal systems capable of handling text, images, and audio inputs.

LLMs Pre-Training The pre-training stage of large models in the context of adopting neural network-based solutions has proven to be particularly important. The ability to reduce the dependence on a labeled dataset and capture the structuring knowledge of the formation of a language independent of domain-specific content has proven to be very important. This has been particularly relevant, especially in the context of model reuse [Zhao *et al.*, 2024], enabling few-shot or zero-shot paradigms for specific task-solving (as the model does not need to be extensively further trained with a big domain-specific dataset, or even further trained at all).

Like previously defined, BERT is a model pre-trained on a large unlabeled text corpus using self-supervised learning with two key training paradigms: Masked Language Modeling (MLM) and Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) [Rogers *et al.*, 2020]. MLM is used to predict randomly masked words in a sentence as typically 15% of the words on the training dataset are replaced with a “mask” token. An example of a training data sample can be identified as follows.

Alice told Bob how much she [MASK] him.

As the model predicts the correct word, this approach makes the context truly bidirectional, as the input contemplated the entire string. This contemplates a token-by-token context understanding training to a sentence. It’s loss function is formalized in Equation 1.

$$\mathcal{L}_{MLM} = - \sum_{i \in M} \log P(w_i | X_{\setminus M}) \quad (1)$$

Where M is the set of masked token positions, w_i is the correct word at position i , $X_{\setminus M}$ is the input sequence excluding the masked words and $P(w_i | X_{\setminus M})$ is the model’s predicted probability of the correct word.

The NSP training paradigm assigns a macro understanding of a textual corpus to a model. An example of a training data sample for this paradigm can be identified as follows.

Sentence A: Alice told Bob how much she loves him.
Sentence B: Pizza has been very expensive recently.
Sentence C: Alice should marry Bob very soon!

In this step, the model predicts what is the next sentence in a training dataset for a given input. In this example, given Sentence A, the model is trained to predict that Sentence C is more relevant to the continuity of what is presented as a result than Sentence B. It’s loss function is formalized in Equation 2.

$$\mathcal{L}_{NSP} = - [y \log P(y) + (1 - y) \log(1 - P(y))] \quad (2)$$

Where y is the ground truth label (1 if the second sentence follows the first, 0 otherwise) and $P(y)$ is the model’s predicted probability that the second sentence follows the first.

Therefore, the training loss is the sum of the MLM likelihood and the mean NSP likelihood in the process of updating weights for each neuron in the network [Aroca-Ouellette and Rudzicz, 2020], formalized given Equation 3.

$$\mathcal{L}_{BERT} = \mathcal{L}_{MLM} + \mathcal{L}_{NSP} \quad (3)$$

As a result, what is widely used as input for NLP applications in general, the so-called textual embeddings, are the result of processing the already trained neural network (with updated weights) in a context-aware vectorized form. A common application for this result is to calculate the cosine similarity between two vectors embedded using the BERT model. Other iterations are a direct result from BERT development with further adaptations, such as the BART [Lewis *et al.*, 2019] and Roberta [Conneau *et al.*, 2020] models, or even models specialized in the Portuguese language, such as Bertimbau [Souza *et al.*, 2020] and Tucano [Corrêa *et al.*, 2024]. Even in the context of more complete and recent models, BERT-based models are still widely used in tasks such as classification tasks and specific Q&A situations [Hugging Face, 2025a].

More complex models, like Meta’s Llama and Open Ai’s GPT, are initially trained on a Causal Language Modeling (CLM) paradigm. They use a transformer architecture based on encoder and decoder [Vaswani *et al.*, 2023]. In this context, for the use that will be given in this work, it is important to define that the resultant model reflects a probability distribution over sequences of words by predicting each token at a time. This means that the model is supposed to understand the context until a certain point of the input, and update the context itself at each token provided. An example of a training data sample for this paradigm can be identified as follows.

Input: "Alice told"
Output: "him"

Input: "Alice told Bob"
Output: "that"

Input: "Alice told Bob that she"
Output: "loves"

Input: "Alice told Bob that she loves"
Output: "him"

The result is the ability to quickly generate human-like text using human input given a certain context window, depending on each model deployed. Therefore, the loss function is given by the negative log-likelihood (cross-entropy loss) for each token in the sequence, formalized in Equation 4.

$$\mathcal{L}_{CLM} = - \sum_{t=1}^T \log P(x_t | x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{t-1}) \quad (4)$$

An understanding of specific further training for model adaptation is presented in Section 4.2, which is applicable to a range of models even if based on different training logics and particular architecture implementations.

4.2 Further Applications of Modern LLMs

An out-of-the-box implementation of an Large Language Model will not always be sufficient to meet the requirements stipulated by a business domain, given an specific stipulated objective. At times, the dataset on which an LLM was originally trained does not encompass specific private data, or

Figure 2. Visualization of a RAG system.

does not reflect the desired writing mannerisms of a specific author or group. In order to personalize the use of a generalist model, there are specific paradigms to obtain certain behaviors or information retrieval. In this context, two main categories of approaches are introduced: Retrieval-Augmented Generation and Model Fine-Tuning.

Retrieval Aumented Generation Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [Gao et al., 2024a] enables the use of private or personalized textual data by injecting relevant retrieved content into the prompt alongside the user’s query. Instead of retraining the model, RAG systems rely on external context retrieved from a vector database, making the model a fixed component and shifting the development focus to text retrieval infrastructure. This results in faster deployment and reduced costs.

RAG pipelines typically involve encoding private data into embeddings stored in a vector database. At query time, the system retrieves the most relevant entries by comparing them with the embedding of the user’s question: These retrieved texts form the input context for the LLM, as shown in Figure 2.

RAG implementations often include customizable stages such as query refinement, ranking strategies for relevant results, and support for various vector databases like **Chroma DB** and **Pinecone**. Due to high industry demand, low-code platforms like **Langflow** have emerged to simplify RAG deployment.

Fine-tuning Unlike RAGs, the fine-tuning process involves further training models for specific tasks, directly affecting the pre-trained weights of a model (transfer learning) [Parthasarathy et al., 2024]. Thus, the only way to change how a model generates its response in a RAG-based system is through prompt engineering [Sahoo et al., 2024]. In the case of fine-tuning, a new training step occurs with a domain-specific textual corpus, expectedly of much smaller magnitude when compared to the model’s original pre-training dataset. Fine-tuned models are better able to recreate the way text is generated, not just repeating what is passed in a contextual window. Exemplifying the difference in the application of both approaches, fine-tuning a model would be able to recreate the way an author writes given a representative but not necessarily too extensive dataset, while a RAG would be better suited for a simple Q&A system that handles large volumes of data that are frequently updated [Parthasarathy et al., 2024].

A common complication in the deployment of fine-tuning models is related to the computational cost involved in the

process of changing weights in the original neural network. Thus, different methods for fine-tuning have emerged from the need to make this approach more accessible.

Methodologies include [Anisuzzaman et al., 2025], but are not limited to:

- Naive fine-tuning: load the entire model and follow the training in the same way as pre-training did. A notoriously costly approach.
- Parameter-efficient fine-tuning: PEFT-based fine-tuning has the overall objective of optimizing naive processes. The basic way in which this happens is by updating only a limited subset of weights in the network from an original model given a specific methodology. In this category of fine-tuning we find notable approaches such as LORA [Hu et al., 2021], QLora [Dettmers et al., 2023] and Dora [Liu et al., 2024].
- Pruning: this process involve directly removing redundant parameters from a original model in order to make the model’s computing less costly and more time efficient.
- Quantization: this approach involves loading and manipulating models using data types smaller than typical floating points commonly used in naive fine-tuning. It is assumed that the loss of precision in the representation of information does not sufficiently affect the gain in the fine-tuning process since the information that needs to be adjusted is only found in a subset of the entire set of original weights.

Hybrid LLM approaches involve fine-tuned models combined with domain-specific information retrieval. For example, modeling an online store attendant requires generating responses aligned with corporate guidelines while dynamically retrieving specific data such as product prices, catalog availability, or operating hours [Parthasarathy et al., 2024]. It is common for the fine-tuning process to occur through the support of Hugging Face’s Python libraries or via a corporate solution such as OpenAI’s low-code fine-tuning system.

QLoRA: Quantized Low Rank Adaptation QLora is a way of optimizing the fine-tuning process that extends the application of the LoRA algorithm, being a structuring enabler for the results obtained in this article. This methodology applies two principles introduced earlier in Section 4.1 of this article: Quantization and Low-Rank Adaptation, being a type of Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) [Parthasarathy et al., 2024].

PEFT methodologies such as QLora, Lora and Dora work through a system of Adapters within the neural network that maintain their original weights preserved, so that a matrix of lesser complexity is trained (the Adapter module) instead of the entire model with all the existing weights. Consequently, the implementation of an Adapter is independent of the original network architecture, being highly reusable. Instead of changing the weights in the network, all that is trained is the displacement that the original weight output must perform to comply with the new task in the new training stage. It ends up being the responsibility of the developer carrying

out the fine-tuning process to simply choose in which part of the network the adapter is allocated.

Thus, the optimization obtained through the application of QLoRA does not only occur through the use of an Adapter, but also through the fact that the original network being trained (traditionally 32-bits) is compressed to 4 bits, then being the part of quantification in the process. The result is that the application of this method successfully approximates naive fine-tuning in several test scenarios, and enables faster training on less powerful hardware.

To understand how or why QLoRA works, it is necessary to understand the application of regular Low-Rank Adaptation [Hu *et al.*, 2021]. The mathematical intuition that underpins the process is that of approximation by low-rank matrices [Kumar and Shneider, 2016]. The *rank* of a matrix is defined as the number of linearly independent rows or columns, which corresponds to the dimension of the vector space spanned by its rows or columns. This value is always less than or equal to the smaller of the matrix’s number of rows and columns.

If rank of a matrix is significantly lower than the minimum value between the number of rows and columns, then that matrix is considered to be of a low rank. Therefore, exemplified by Equations 5 and 6, respectively, a full-rank and a low-rank matrix.

$$\text{rank} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 5 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 9 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \right) = 3 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{rank} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 4 & 6 \end{bmatrix} \right) = 1 \quad (6)$$

By formalizing operations between low-rank matrices, it is possible to define how this property propagates in multiplications used in the final QLoRA application. Let A and B be matrices with ranks $m = \text{rank}(A)$ and $n = \text{rank}(B)$. The rank of their product is constrained as shown in Equation 7:

$$\text{rank}(AB) \leq \min(m, n) \quad (7)$$

The rank of a matrix can be perceived as the dimensions of the feature space it represents. In this context, a low-rank matrix of a certain size reflects fewer features than a full-rank matrix of the same dimensions, remaining manipulable in operations while spending a smaller amount of computational resources. Consequently, the intuition is that the low-rank matrix that represents the desired weight change directly reflects only a subset of the entire network, only the weights of interest that reflect the features that the fine-tuning process wants to change. A domain-specific dataset (such as a medical or legal domain) affects a smaller set of weights than a dataset that trains a model to generate tokens in an entirely new language. Therefore, Low-Rank Adaptation of LLMs is a model agnostic approach, in a way that is independent of certain specificities in the model architecture. It is treated as an add-on approach.

Therefore, Low-Rank Adaptation affects the weights during model training by using an Adapter module containing a matrix of low intrinsic rank (these being the numbers updating during training forward pass).

The update matrix W is composed of two low-rank matrices B and A , of a low rank r . This implies that the forward pass of the layer in training, originally W , is modified to the product of A and B as seen on Equation 8.

$$W_{out} = W_{original} + BA \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the low-rank portion of the equation can be defined as W given Equation 9.

$$\Delta W = BA \quad (9)$$

Subsequently, a random Gaussian initialization is used, so the product of A and B at the start of training is equal to zero. The update matrix A times B is additionally scaled with a factor α divided by the predefined rank of the matrix, as seen on Equation 10.

$$W_{out} = W_{original} + \frac{\alpha \Delta W}{r} \quad (10)$$

The scaling factor is seen as a “tradeoff control” of how much is desired to change the model with each step in training. The rank “ r ” is predefined as a parameter in training and remains static. The higher the rank, the larger the matrix that will maintain W is, representing a larger feature space. The larger the module that changes the network weights, the greater the chance of hallucination in the final output of the network. Controlling the scaling factor and the rank size of the update matrix is a development choice and is directly affected by the domain of the desired fine-tuning application. However, a rule of thumb for the first hyperparameter testing that has been proven to be efficient in previous studies [Biderman *et al.*, 2024] can be defined using Equation 11.

$$\alpha = 2r \quad (11)$$

With the logic behind LoRA [Hu *et al.*, 2021] well defined, QLoRA [Dettmers *et al.*, 2023] works in the same way, but compressing the model to a smaller data type. Using the PEFT Python libraries [Mangrulkar *et al.*, 2022], this implementation is relatively transparent and easy to implement.

5 Pipeline for AI-Generated News Detection

In this Section, given the more relevant theoretical basis introduced previously, the architecture of the proposed solution of this article will be introduced. The step-by-step process from data extraction to the final operation of the models and tests to be performed to obtain a satisfactory final result are further explained in greater detail. Decisions of the solution are also further elaborated, such as the rationale behind the auxiliary model as an intermediate step and the process of generating and normalizing inputs for classification.

5.1 Architecture

The simplified process of the pipeline [OMG, 2011] is demonstrated in Figure 3.

Likewise, the process is explained in three primary stages:

Figure 3. Pipeline shown as simple single-lane BPMN [OMG, 2011] process.

- **Data Acquisition:** This step refers to web scraping, acquiring external data for validation and basic string normalization. Data may also be obtained from public datasets for validation with other sources of the model generated at the end of the pipeline (strictly not for the intermediate model). These results are used to compose a dataset that will serve as input to generate news using the auxiliary model.
- **Auxiliary Generator Model Fine-Tuning:** This step refers to fine-tuning a model that reproduces text as the originally extracted corpus. At this stage, an intermediate methodology within the pipeline is also inserted to generate inputs with this model, which will be used by the main classification model. The objective is to take the original news and have a direct pair generated by AI, consolidating the dataset with two labels for classification by the final model.
- **Classification Model Fine-Tuning:** Given the different datasets generated depending on the models used on the intermediate stage, a LLM is fine-tuned for binary textual classification to differentiate if the given input is generated by an LLM or is a human-made text.

5.2 Data Acquisition

The data acquisition process involves web scraping recent online publications to collect original news from open-domain sources in late 2024. This dataset will serve both in the final stage of the process to compose a validation dataset (which the generated classification models must classify correctly) and will serve as partial input for the auxiliary news generator model. The objective is to obtain a defined number of news items, in the thousands. There should be news items not used in the intermediate model so that the classifier model can use them for validation at the end of the pipeline.

It is desirable that the output of this step consists of more than one source, and that a complete news item is extracted. This includes the news title, the subhead, the full body text of the news item, and the source website for traceability. Images should be discarded since only the text generation will be taken into consideration, however advertisements and other texts that are included in the news must be incorporated.

This is important so that the auxiliary model may also be able to replicate the way the text is presented to the reader, and not just the linguistic choices that are part of a language itself.

In the use case presented in this work for Portuguese news text, data extraction in Python will be used using the Beautiful Soup library [Richardson, 2007].

5.3 Auxiliary Generator Model Fine-Tuning

The main objective of conceptualizing an auxiliary model is to create a dataset for the classification stage. Given real inputs extracted previously, an auxiliary model must replicate these inputs through the particularities of an LLM. The focus is not on the process of reproducing the extracted information with a language model, but rather on reproducing the linguistic choices of a journalist in low fidelity to the originally obtained facts. As is understood, this is the point of what careless speech is by definition and why it is concerning. At this stage, models of sufficient complexity should be tested to generate long strings, and, in a manual validation stage, generated outputs should resemble journalistic texts. It is important that the text generated at this step has an order of magnitude similar to the original text extracted. For short news, it was observed that this number is around 200 words. The complexity of the models tested to obtain good results often requires the use of PEFT techniques, such as quantization and LORA.

Another alternative would be to use a RAG system at this stage of the process to generate a news article given an example of another article. However, the nature of this approach would not allow it to reproduce the desired journalistic mannerisms and vocabulary as efficiently as a fine-tuned model [Parthasarathy et al., 2024]. This approach is expected to not significantly alter the way a model is written, as the weights of the neural network are not altered at any time. At the same time, the information generated by the system would have a very high probability of reproducing the facts with good fidelity, and this is not the intention [Gao et al., 2024b]. The so-called “careless speech” text generator should not resemble a decent information retrieval engine at any time. For this reason, RAG-based approaches were discarded.

For the process to work end-to-end, at least one generating model is required. However, this step can be done for multiple models, which will probably result in more than one classifier in the end, given the multiple datasets to be classified.

Motivation for Fine-Tuning an Auxiliary Generator Model

The intention is to reproduce the best scenario for adapting an LLM for news generation (with malicious intentions or not), being an input more enriched in nature than an out-of-the-box model used with pure prompt engineering [Sahoo et al., 2024]. The result of integrating this model is to best contemplate the nuances present in journalistic writing itself. Therefore, this approach enhances the string differentiation potential of the final classifier model by integrating into the pipeline a case that is at first glance dismissible, but has inherently a high chance of bypassing the final classifier as LLM models evolve and get better at adapting to domain-specific tasks.

Figure 4. Demonstration of generating an LLM news text based on a real news article. All text generated by this process is subsequently normalized. Each news story is composed of a headline, a subheading, and a collection of statements or facts. When a news story is recreated using partial information as input, the rest of the information created presents a specific theme but with low fidelity.

Figure 5. News generation with a real input and a pair generated by LLM.

Standardized Generation of Synthetic News Text The auxiliary generator model is used to generate synthetic news given a methodology to standardize the prompt. Every prompt is systematically generated in the same way, and then normalized (or discarded if the generated string is too short, but this occurs as an exception treatment). For each sample of human-made news, the model goes through a process of flattening the information, in order to recreate the input in low fidelity of facts. A visual representation can be seen in Figure 4.

The result is a real news dataset (extracted by web scraping) and its direct pair recreated by an auxiliary model of that same topic, this being the input of the classification model. The premise of this process is that, when classifying a volume of news on the same topic (in a pairwise logic), what will palpably differentiate them are the writing decisions and recreated facts, not the differences in topics. This process is then instantiated in BPMN [OMG, 2011] in Figure 5. If volumes of data on different topics were classified without curating the subjects of each input, there would be a risk of classifying not whether an input is generated by LLM or not, but rather the topics of each dataset (if, for example, in one dataset there is more news about sports and in another sample there is more news about politics regardless of the origin of the data). This would constitute string subject classification in a multiclass paradigm but without proper labels, It is another problem in data science entirely.

At this stage of the process, tests can also be carried out to determine how models without fine-tuning perform when applied in the same large-volume generation pipeline.

5.4 Classification Model Fine-Tuning

The goal of this main step is to fine-tune more than one model on different cases previously raised to detect whether a text was generated by LLM or not. The idea is to reuse a small LLM that fits this use case and test different parameters to obtain models that perform well in the desired context. For example, in case the auxiliary model is based on Llama, identify models that perform well on the dataset made by Llama or desired related use cases. Therefore, the combination of different models with different previously generated datasets allows for the acquisition of several use cases with the ultimate goal of detecting “careless speech” from different sources.

At this stage, adopting PEFT-based approaches is unnecessary since the classifier’s training time is already short. Instead, a few hyperparameters, such as learning rates and batch sizes, are manually tested. The initial hyperparameter settings are shown in Table 1.

	Set A	Set B	Set C
Number of Epochs	3	3	5
Train Batch Size	16	32	8
Learning Rate	$2e^{-5}$	$5e^{-5}$	$1e^{-5}$
Weight Decay	0.01	0.01	0.1

Table 1. Comparison of Fine-Tuning Hyperparameters for Classification.

The result of this pipeline is expected to include different models for different use cases. It is also expected that at this stage, a curation of which model will be effectively used as a result of the pipeline should occur manually as well as automatically (based on classical evaluation metrics [Wang and Wang, 2022]). It is expected that models that perform with good metrics in the training stage will be analyzed with new validation datasets generated (or scraped from online sources) as demonstrated in the previous stages. The validation stage for these models consists of using the model to classify inputs from different sources to then measure performance.

6 Results

For this case study with news in Brazilian Portuguese, the generating model is limited to just a few cases, but the pipeline can be readily extended to a larger number of sources. All testing and training were performed using a consumer-grade GPU supported by the Hugging Face Library, except for the tests that were conducted with the fine-tuning suite and use of low-code platforms developed by OpenAI [OpenAI, 2024].

6.1 Extracted Dataset for Brazilian News

The extracted dataset consists of news scraped from Brazilian newsroom websites that are not blocked to the non-paying user with a subscription service, specifically in the period from the end of the year 2024. There is no filtering of collected topics, so there is news on topics relevant to Brazilian politics as well as news sponsored by external advertisers.

An overview of the dataset obtained in the web scraping process previously described can be seen in Table 2.

News Articles Extracted	20.070
Websites Consulted	2
Amount of Words - News Title	241.429
Amount of Words - News Description	449.493
Amount of Words - News Body	6.667.037

Table 2. Statistic on the scraped dataset.

Regarding the privacy of the entities involved, mentions of the original sources are properly anonymized in this text corpora. Despite this, like other models available online such as ChatGPT [OpenAI, 2024], modern LLMs are properly capable of reproducing text that mentions publicly exposed persons that are found in the original training dataset. Therefore, strings referring to names and places were not anonymized.

Given the tests carried out and the complexity of the intermediate model fine-tuning process, only a subset of this dataset is used in the intermediate stage as input for model fine-tuning, but this dataset is later used in its entirety for validation.

6.2 Artificial Data Generation

Small and medium-sized models (up to about 8 billion parameters) extracted from Hugging Face were tested in this step, with the proposal of identifying a highly efficient candidate model that could achieve the task of generating texts similar to journalistic news for a proof of concept. The chosen models at this step are further used as a generator for inputs in a classification model, as shown in Section 5.

The results of small models such as GPT-2 and GPT-Neo have not proven sufficient in generating strings of similar size to the target, despite being models small enough to be trained on limited hardware and without any optimization. When approaching models with a higher number of parameters, the results obtained became more satisfactory even when trained on limited hardware, with the use of a moderately sized dataset when compared to the original and well-applied optimization techniques as previously demonstrated. This was a point of great relevance in this study, when applying previous experiences of fine-tuning language models it was discovered that the benefits of using large datasets are only marginal.

Therefore, it is understood that there is a point in the size of an ideal dataset for this task at which the metrics obtained are good enough [Vieira *et al.*, 2024]. Using only the sample size of the original dataset of around 30% made it possible for the training to converge within a few training epochs for models that have around 8 billion parameters, like Mistral and Llama 3. Ultimately, a fine-tuned model of Llama 3 with 8 billion parameters was the model that resulted in more acceptable profile of strings. As a brief manual evaluation step, when using the model for generating batch text generation, results showed that this model has the ability of making complete sentences that were large enough in size when compared to other models which failed at times.

Simultaneously at this stage, a model was fine-tuned with OpenAI's low code platform with the aim of comparing the

model that had its fine-tuning optimized using the Hugging Face library with a model made with software that makes such decisions transparent to the user. The model chosen for this task was "gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18" which has a more affordable cost when compared to the full-sized GPT-4 and would be the model comparable to the 8 billion parameter Llama model in Open AI's product lineup in later 2024 [Zeff, 2024].

The final classification dataset consists of pairs of recently scraped news articles, representing contemporary Brazilian journalism, and synthetic articles generated by auxiliary models using a pair-wise approach. Additionally, an external dataset with distinct textual characteristics was employed exclusively for validation.

Qualitative Demonstration To demonstrate the work performed in this step, Quote 6.2 represent samples of the text generation capacity of the intermediate models. Common topics are approached in a realistic way, imitating the text of conventional journalistic writing. Names of entities and places are generated, which may or may not be consistent with reality.

Prompt to fine-tuned GPT4-o Model: "Responda como um jornalista, que irá publicar um texto em um jornal online de ampla circulação. Escreva uma notícia com o título: 'Após ser assaltado em um restaurante na 412 Sul, o cantor e compositor [redacted] foi encontrado morto dentro do carro, na madrugada desta segunda-feira (2/10)'".

Synthetic News Text: "Após ser assaltado em um restaurante na 412 Sul, o cantor e compositor [redacted] foi encontrado morto dentro do carro, na madrugada desta segunda-feira (2/10). O corpo estava no porta-malas de um veículo roubado. O crime aconteceu por volta das 21h30 deste domingo (1º/10), no restaurante Casa da Costela. Segundo a Polícia Militar, [redacted] e uma mulher estavam saindo do local quando foram abordados por dois homens armados. Os suspeitos levaram o carro da vítima, aparelhos celulares e outros pertences pessoais. A dupla fugiu em direção à Avenida Hélio Prates. De acordo com informações preliminares da PMDF, o corpo foi encontrado dentro do porta-malas de um carro roubado na QNL 23 de Taguatinga Norte. A vítima teria sido morta a tiros e os criminosos teriam tentado ocultar o cadáver colocando-o no porta-malas do veículo que havia sido furtado no domingo (1º/10). Uma equipe do Corpo de Bombeiros Militar (CBMDF) esteve no local para remover o corpo para perícia e a Polícia Civil isolou a área para realizar os primeiros levantamentos periciais. Ainda não há informações sobre as circunstâncias exatas da morte nem sobre a motivação do crime."

Prompt to fine-tuned LLama Model: "Responda como um jornalista, que irá publicar um texto em um jornal online de ampla circulação. Escreva uma notícia com o título: 'Economia tem expansão de 1,74% no 3º trimestre, indica BC.'".

Synthetic News Text: “Economia tem expansão de 1,74% no 3º trimestre, indica BC. O Banco Central (BC) divulgou nesta quinta-feira (12/10) o resultado do Índice de Atividade Econômica (IAE) do 2º semestre de julho a dezembro de, que indica a expansão do PIB de nove meses. O indicador do BC aponta para um crescimento de um ano e três meses de - 0,17 % no ano, contra o -0.22% previsto anteriormente. A taxa de crescimento do ano passado foi de + 4,00 %. O IAE é um indicativo do crescimento do Produto Interno Bruto (PIB) no curto prazo. No trimestre, o indicado apontou para uma expansão de 1.74 % na economia no terceiro trimestre de janeiro a setembro. Na comparação com os mesmos meses do segundo trimestre de último ano (janeiro de setembro a março de este ano), o IPEA apoiou uma queda de atividade de - 5,4 % (em comparação ao trimestre anterior, foi -1 %). O BC dividiu o ano em quatro períodos, de acordo com a evolução do Ipea: de fevereiro até junho, a economia teve um resultado negativo de - 8,7 %; de junho a agosto, -2,8 %; de agosto a outubro, +0 9,3 % e, finalmente, em outubro a novembro, 6,5 %. A estimativa do Banco Central para o quarto trimestre é de uma alta de cerca de dois pontos percentuais.”

The text generated by Llama’s fine-tuning presents occasional typing errors, which are easily corrected by text normalizers. The same does not occur, or occurs to a lesser extent, in the text generated by GPT-4’s fine-tuning.

6.3 Efficiency

Using 5 thousand samples made it possible to fine-tune an instance of an acceptable language model on consumer-grade hardware for a proof-of-concept. Decisions related to the efficiency of fine-tuning models not only directly affect the cost but also the carbon footprint of each model, and for specific cases simpler models may be sufficient for the stipulated task.

A simple estimate of the carbon footprint [Lacoste *et al.*, 2019] used in the auxiliary model fine-tuning (the most costly part of the pipeline) can be seen in Table 3.

	GPT-4o mini	Llama 3 8B
Hours to fine-tune	2 hours	6 hours
Samples used	17000	5000
Hardware	NVIDIA A100 ¹	RTX 4070 S
Carbon Footprint	0.18 kg CO2 eq.	0.71 kg CO2 eq.

Table 3. Comparison of Fine-Tuning Hardware Specifications for each case proposed.

Assuming that the efficiency of the RTX 4070 Super is mostly comparable to the RTX 3080, it can be concluded that this approach has a larger carbon footprint than using a traditional datacenter Nvidia A100. However, comparing this consumer hardware-based approach with industrial hardware is particularly tricky. Especially with the objective of

¹Undisclosed hardware, used only for workload estimation.

comparing the approaches used in this article with the Llama model and GPT-4o mini model used.

In reality, the hardware employed in Open Ai’s platform is undisclosed, and there is a plausible chance of having multiple GPUs employed in the process. The comparison in Table 3 is only appropriate for single-GPU scenarios. In any case, the time taken to train on the Open Ai platform is compatible with the efficiency of an Nvidia A100, making an efficiency analysis maintain its validity. All the demanding fine-tuning experiments in this article are likely to take less than 1 kilogram of equivalent carbon dioxide, or a value in that order of magnitude.

Final Datasets for Training Multiple Classification Models An overview of the dataset obtained for the classification process can be seen in Table 4. This represents the amount of textual inputs in total per auxiliary model, including real and generated news pairs.

Base Model	Fine-Tuned	Quantity
GPT-4o	No	4000
GPT-4o	Yes	6000
LLaMA 3 8B	No	4000
LLaMA 3 8B	Yes	2000
Total		16000

Table 4. News generated for classification experiment by base model and fine-tuning status.

6.4 Final Classification Model

To evaluate the effectiveness of the Hugging face library to fine tune BERT models, its results are compared against traditional machine learning models trained on different text embeddings.

The use of fine-tuning not only for textual generation but also for classification allows for high code reuse and few changes in the generated dataset, representing the original pipeline proposal. This type of solution also represents the use of a more complex model, potentially covering cases that would not be possible in simpler algorithms.

The machine learning approach consists of testing of the following models with a five-fold cross-validation:

- Random Forest
- Decision Tree
- Gradient Boosting Classifier
- Logistic Regression
- Naive Bayes

In this baseline scenario three different embeddings are tested as input:

- Bart [Lewis *et al.*, 2019]
- Bert [Conneau *et al.*, 2020]
- Roberta [Conneau *et al.*, 2020]

Furthermore, the model chosen for use in the classification tool through the Hugging Face fine-tuning library [Hugging Face, 2025b] was BERT, which constitutes the classification

approach also based on LLM fine-tuning. Other models optimized for Portuguese can be used at this stage, but it is understood that a base model such as BERT is already capable of being an efficient classifier for a proof of concept scenario. More specific models for different domains can be applied in different pipeline applications, and for this case study the application of models such as Bertimbau [Souza *et al.*, 2020] and Sabiá [Pires *et al.*, 2023b] constitute future iterations. Using a task-specific fine-tuned LLM is possible by adding a classification module on top of the trained network. Traditionally, this addition to the original neural network can be a simple fully connected layer that maps the model's output to the desired number of classes. This process is made entirely transparent for the user in this application.

Despite BERT being a smaller model than the auxiliary models, it is known that for classification a model of this magnitude is considered enough [Bucher and Martini, 2024]. A smaller model also allows a fine-tuning process in a short time and without the need for PEFT-based approaches. As a result, for each training dataset (represented in Table 4) and for 3 different predefined set of hyperparameters (represented in Table 1), a BERT-variant fine-tuned model is generated.

An extra scenario was conducted for an experiment in which different auxiliary source models were mixed in the classification dataset. Each auxiliary model has 2000 inputs in this dataset, with no differentiation of auxiliary model, just a label that indicates whether a given string was generated by a LLM. The aim was to understand whether mixing data from different sources would be of greater value to the model's ability to generalize the final result.

The approach in this part experiment totals 12 models, while in the traditional machine learning approach the combination of 5 models with 3 embedding categories as input for each training dataset (with the inclusion of an extra test scenario in which all datasets are combined into one) totals to 75 models.

Performance of Traditional Machine Learning Classification Models When analyzing the training data, it has been observed that the accuracy of the models was, in general, satisfactory. The average training accuracy was 83.71%, and only 20 models out of 75 obtained overall accuracy below 80% (and were then systematically considered to be of insufficient performance for further validation). To truly understand whether the results were satisfactory, some models of interest were chosen to move on to the validation stage. At this stage, human-made news from online news sources were also classified for validation, alongside synthetic text.

Even on good training metrics, some models failed to generalize continuous classification to new cases. It is observed that differentiating the inputs generated by GPT-4 is significantly more complex than other cases of inputs generated by Llama (as seen on models shown in Appendix A). Some models presented good quality for specific use, as demonstrated in Tables 5 and 6.

When analyzing the generated model metrics, it is understood that many models failed to generalize well to out-of-sample data. Models trained with specific datasets tend to obtain satisfactory results in cases of classification of strings

Dataset	Label 0	Label 1	Total	Acc. (%)
LLaMA 8B	1488	632	2120	29.81
LLaMA 8B (FT)	39	943	982	96.03
GPT-4 (FT)	1567	1433	3000	47.77
GPT-4 (FT, val)	814	686	1500	45.73
GPT-4	1998	2	2000	0.10
Human (orig.)	13366	4107	17473	76.50
Human (ext.)	2775	225	3000	92.50

Table 5. Validation for a Random Forest model trained over synthetic news made with fine-tuned Llama model. Each single dataset in validation is associated with a single correct class (AI or human, Label 0 and Label 1 respectively). This model proved to be efficient in identifying text that was also generated by the same intermediate model, as it is the case with other models.

Dataset	Label 0	Label 1	Total	Acc. (%)
LLaMA 8B	1134	986	2120	46.51
LLaMA 8B (FT)	978	4	982	0.41
GPT-4 (FT)	2273	727	3000	24.23
GPT-4 (FT, val)	1060	440	1500	29.33
GPT-4	81	1919	2000	95.95
Human (orig.)	15036	2437	17473	86.05
Human (ext.)	2523	477	3000	84.10

Table 6. Validation for a Decision Tree model trained over synthetic news made with GPT4-o. While models may excel in specific cases like original GPT-4 generations, generalized classification across diverse input origins remains challenging.

from that same origin model. In other words, a model trained with a dataset generated by GPT-4 is most likely to perform poorly when classifying an input generated by Llama, and vice versa. For a model to be considered satisfactory, it must not only obtain good accuracy in a specific dataset (being suitable for a use case) but must also present good accuracy to classify inputs generated by humans (as seen on Tables 5 and 6). It is understood that in this case study, false positives are of high risk for the business context, since it would falsely accuse a journalist of using AI (characterizing a potential fake news).

When classifying datasets containing text from different sources, the model trained on combined datasets achieved better average results across all validation scenarios. However, its performance on specific classes was lower than models specifically trained on corresponding data sources. For instance, a Naive Bayes model classifying BART embeddings, trained on mixed-source data, achieved only 74.76% accuracy on inputs generated by Llama without fine-tuning. In contrast, a Logistic Regression model classifying BERT embeddings, specifically trained on data generated by Llama, reached 93.87% accuracy for the same validation task. Complete results for this scenario are shown in Table 7.

Dataset	Label 0	Label 1	Total	Acc. (%)
LLaMA 8B	535	1585	2120	74.76
LLaMA 8B (FT)	25	957	982	97.45
GPT-4 (FT)	558	2442	3000	81.40
GPT-4 (FT, val)	327	1173	1500	78.20
GPT-4	1140	860	2000	43.00
Human (orig.)	10001	7472	17473	57.24
Human (ext.)	1912	1088	3000	63.73

Table 7. Validation for a Naive Bayes model trained over a merged dataset synthetic news of multiple sources. This model shows decent discriminative ability in particular cases, but fails to identify real news. In the context of other single-use models, it represents a worse result.

The validation results for the subset of tested models can be seen in the Appendix A.

Results of Fine-Tuning for Classification Satisfactory results were obtained from this stage of the pipeline. The full fine-tuning process occurred in less than 5 minutes for each training dataset scenario, without the need for further optimizations. With the data consolidated in the previous steps, the models generated at this stage represent the final outputs to be deployed according to the pipeline proposed in Section 5. In the traditional machine learning approach with embeddings, the process of externally saving the semantic vectors of each dataset proved to be more time-consuming than the actual full fine-tuning process. The model evaluation performed was analogous to the traditional machine learning approach, in which some models with good training metrics were chosen for an extra validation pipeline. The Cross-Entropy Loss for a limited number of epochs remained at 0.1 on average for all models, and the training accuracy averaged 97%. More expressive results that validate the possibility of classification were obtained as a result of further evaluation of single models.

The fine-tuned BERT model presented in Table 8 illustrates the best-case scenario from this phase of the pipeline. Specifically, for news generated by GPT-4 (fine-tuned or original), the classifier achieved over 90% accuracy on previously unseen validation inputs, highlighting its strong generalization capability. Additionally, training on data from a fine-tuned GPT-4 model improved the classifier’s accuracy even on inputs generated by the original, non-fine-tuned model. This suggests that enriching the training dataset with data from fine-tuned models can enhance classification performance in certain cases, although this outcome was not consistently observed across all tested models.

Dataset	Label 0	Label 1	Total	Acc. (%)
LLaMA 8B	1500	620	2120	29.25
LLaMA 8B (FT)	818	164	982	16.70
GPT-4 (FT)	0	3000	3000	100.00
GPT-4 (FT, val)	2	1498	1500	99.87
GPT-4	35	1965	2000	98.25
Human (orig.)	16843	630	17473	96.39
Human (ext.)	2994	6	3000	99.80

Table 8. Fine-tuned BERT model trained over fine-tuned GPT-4 synthetic strings. GPT-4 fine-tuned models demonstrated near-perfect classification performance, while Llama-made data models showed lower accuracy. This result, considering the case of classification of a single origin model, appears to be a result as good as or better than the result observed in the machine learning approach.

Similarly, It was also possible to validate a fine-tuned BERT model trained with Llama with good results, although the accuracy in detecting real news dropped significantly once compared to the model in Table 8. This drop in accuracy for this class represents a potential risk if this model is deployed by itself but reinforces the potential for using these models together in an ensemble for model-specific classification. It was possible to maintain accuracy above 90% for some validation datasets, as can be seen in Table 9.

The validation results for the subset of tested models can be seen in the Appendix B.

Comparison of Classification Approaches A traditional machine learning approach, even if simplified, requires additional development time in an already extensive process.

Dataset	Label 0	Label 1	Total	Acc. (%)
LLaMA 8B	951	1169	2120	55.14
LLaMA 8B (FT)	5	977	982	99.49
GPT-4 (FT)	221	2779	3000	92.63
GPT-4 (FT, val)	68	1432	1500	95.47
GPT-4	1528	472	2000	23.60
Human (orig.)	11212	6261	17473	64.17
Human (ext.)	2504	496	3000	83.47

Table 9. Fine-tuned BERT model trained over fine-tuned Llama synthetic strings. Fine-tuned models continue to show strong results, especially in GPT-4 and Llama data.

This approach should represent a significant gain for the paradigm shift in programming and the extra work required for development, which is not the case. Some of the models tested in the validation stage reinforce the potential to effectively differentiate the origins of a text focusing on journalistic news in Brazilian Portuguese. However, the potential of having just one model that satisfies all mapped use cases (source of AI-generated text) has proven mostly unfeasible. A highly plausible explanation for why this occurs is that the text bodies used to train the models originally differ from each other, consequently differing in the writing behavior of the final output for the user. The exact composition of the original training dataset for both GPT-4 and Llama 3 8B are not publicly available, despite being an open-weights model. In the context of an ongoing development of a model pipeline, different specific-purpose models operate better in a bagging context.

Even so, models that differentiated news based on their origin were obtainable. This proves the functionality of this proposal given the proper curation of models with better efficiency for multiple LLMs of origin in a context of an ensemble of multiple classifiers for specific use cases.

7 Conclusion

Other works have presented significant advances in the detection of news generated by AI, however, presenting structural differences in their implementations that differ from the result of this work. A plausible result for a proof of concept of an AI-generated news identifier based on continuous fine-tuning of LLM models (as proposed in the established pipeline), integrating a generative model to support the creation of more complex classification inputs. This result supports the combat of the spread of low-effort AI-generated content, often considered spam. Consequently, collaborating to control the dissemination of fake news in an automated and unbiased way. The proposed process could also be expanded to incorporate new and more complex models, consequently productized into social networks or deployed as a product by itself.

The following observations related to the work performed and future developments are then obtained:

- Approaches: Fine-tuning BERT for binary text classification proved to be a valid classification method when compared to a more traditional approach and is less costly in terms of time and development, showing high accuracy in specific scenarios. Therefore, a good approach to get a final use case would be to deploy an ensemble of several models classifying different generator, updating labels accordingly. As seen, one single

resulting model was not able to specialize in all classification cases, but it is possible to choose different models to cover different cases. To improve results already demonstrated as satisfactory in the case study, it is possible to use models specialized in the Portuguese language such as Bertimbau [Souza *et al.*, 2020] and Tucano [Corrêa *et al.*, 2024].

- Alternative scenario for classification of different auxiliary models: Aggregating all possible origins in the same dataset in order to perform binary classification worsened the accuracy of all classes. This further supports the idea that models with segmented datasets for segmented auxiliary models perform better.
- Continuous training: New models that better mimic human speech are released frequently, affecting production costs and even at times a project's scope. An effective classifier relies on inputs from different sources, which points in the direction of a continuous multi-model approach. The use of this pipeline depends on continuous update and retraining, along with the integration of new input models. In other words, there would be the potential for a temporary blind spot for classification as a new model is integrated into the pipeline. The quality and scope of the classified content also depends directly on the corpus obtained for training.
- Need for a Refined Prompt Engineering Process: Currently the process is based on "flattening" data at low fidelity, but this re-creation could be texted at higher fidelity. In other words, to directly include more relevant text in the prompt, refining the prompt engineering process. Topic summarization could be included in guiding the generation of new text. Images used in news articles could also be described and integrated into the pipeline at this point.
- Legal Risks Related to the Data Used: Large-scale production of this pipeline as a high-quality product may depend on approval from multiple journals that would authorize the commercial use of news data. For the purpose of defining this case study, the data obtained is not shared as it is intended for educational purposes only.

7.1 Ethics Statement

It is necessary to reinforce the serious ethical implications of automating the use of LLMs for unsupervised text generation. Human intervention is necessary in many processes to prevent content from being disseminated irresponsibly, ensuring that AI is correctly applied with the aim of making processes more effective rather than creating new problematic dynamics in society.

Declarations

Authors' Contributions

Fernando Xavier, PhD contributed as a manuscript reviewer and consultant. Guilherme Braga also contributed to the conception of this study, performing the necessary experiments, and is the main contributor and writer of this manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Availability of data and materials

Some fine-tuned classifiers that were validated are publicly available in Hugging Face [gui8600k, 2025]. Other datasets (and/or softwares) generated and/or analysed during the current study may be shared upon request.

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A Validation Results: Traditional Approaches

Model	Embedding	Dataset used in classification	Classification Label 0	Classification Label 1	Amount of Data	Goal	Success
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	llama_8b	130	1990	2120	Label 1	93.87%
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	llama_8b_finetuned	375	607	982	Label 1	61.81%
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	gpt4_finetuned	1548	1452	3000	Label 1	48.40%
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	gpt4_finetuned_validation	770	730	1500	Label 1	48.67%
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	gpt4	378	1622	2000	Label 1	81.10%
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	human_original	13573	3900	17473	Label 0	77.68%
LogisticRegression_bert_llama_8b_resultsModel	Bert	human_dataset_externo	2776	224	3000	Label 0	92.53%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	llama_8b	319	1801	2120	Label 1	84.95%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	llama_8b_finetuned	265	717	982	Label 1	73.01%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	gpt4_finetuned	541	2459	3000	Label 1	81.97%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	gpt4_finetuned_validation	268	1232	1500	Label 1	82.13%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	gpt4	255	1745	2000	Label 1	87.25%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	human_original	4008	13465	17473	Label 0	22.94%
GradientBoostingClassifier_bart_gpt4_finetuned_resultsModel	Bert	human_dataset_externo	488	2512	3000	Label 0	16.27%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	llama_8b	535	1585	2120	Label 1	74.76%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	llama_8b_finetuned	25	957	982	Label 1	97.45%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	gpt4_finetuned	558	2442	3000	Label 1	81.40%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	gpt4_finetuned_validation	327	1173	1500	Label 1	78.20%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	gpt4	1140	860	2000	Label 1	43.00%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	human_original	10001	7472	17473	Label 0	57.24%
NaiveBayes_bart_tudo_resultsModel	Bart	human_dataset_externo	1912	1088	3000	Label 0	63.73%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	llama_8b	1488	632	2120	Label 1	29.81%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	llama_8b_finetuned	39	943	982	Label 1	96.03%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	gpt4_finetuned	1567	1433	3000	Label 1	47.77%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	gpt4_finetuned_validation	814	686	1500	Label 1	45.73%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	gpt4	1998	2	2000	Label 1	0.10%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	human_original	13366	4107	17473	Label 0	76.50%
RandomForest_roberta_llama_8b_finetuned_resultsModel	Roberta	human_dataset_externo	2775	225	3000	Label 0	92.50%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	llama_8b	1134	986	2120	Label 1	46.51%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	llama_8b_finetuned	978	4	982	Label 1	0.41%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	gpt4_finetuned	2273	727	3000	Label 1	24.23%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	gpt4_finetuned_validation	1060	440	1500	Label 1	29.33%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	gpt4	81	1919	2000	Label 1	95.95%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	human_original	15036	2437	17473	Label 0	86.05%
DecisionTreeClassifier_roberta_gpt4_resultsModel	Roberta	human_dataset_externo	2523	477	3000	Label 0	84.10%

B Validation Results: BERT Fine-Tuning

Model	Dataset used in classification	Classification Label 0	Classification Label 1	Amount of Data	Goal	Success
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	llama_8b	1500	620	2120	Label 1	29,25%
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	llama_8b_finetuned	818	164	982	Label 1	16,70%
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4_finetuned	0	3000	3000	Label 1	100,00%
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4_finetuned_validation	2	1498	1500	Label 1	99,87%
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4	35	1965	2000	Label 1	98,25%
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	human_original	16843	630	17473	Label 0	96,39%
gpt4_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	human_dataset_externo	2994	6	3000	Label 0	99,80%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	llama_8b	2	2118	2120	Label 1	99,91%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	llama_8b_finetuned	642	340	982	Label 1	34,62%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	gpt4_finetuned	667	2333	3000	Label 1	77,77%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	gpt4_finetuned_validation	295	1205	1500	Label 1	80,33%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	gpt4	19	1981	2000	Label 1	99,05%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	human_original	13268	4205	17473	Label 0	75,93%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setB	human_dataset_externo	2749	251	3000	Label 0	91,63%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	llama_8b	951	1169	2120	Label 1	55,14%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	llama_8b_finetuned	5	977	982	Label 1	99,49%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4_finetuned	221	2779	3000	Label 1	92,63%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4_finetuned_validation	68	1432	1500	Label 1	95,47%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4	1528	472	2000	Label 1	23,60%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	human_original	11212	6261	17473	Label 0	64,17%
llama8b_fine_tuned_bert_multilingual_params_setC	human_dataset_externo	2504	496	3000	Label 0	83,47%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	llama_8b	1187	933	2120	Label 1	44,01%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	llama_8b_finetuned	904	78	982	Label 1	7,94%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	gpt4_finetuned	2314	686	3000	Label 1	22,87%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	gpt4_finetuned_validation	1304	196	1500	Label 1	13,07%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	gpt4	958	1042	2000	Label 1	52,10%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	human_original	17463	10	17473	Label 0	99,94%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setA	human_dataset_externo	2644	356	3000	Label 0	88,13%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	llama_8b	1169	951	2120	Label 1	44,86%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	llama_8b_finetuned	930	52	982	Label 1	5,30%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4_finetuned	2559	441	3000	Label 1	14,70%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4_finetuned_validation	1354	146	1500	Label 1	9,73%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	gpt4	903	1097	2000	Label 1	54,85%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	human_original	17464	9	17473	Label 0	99,95%
gpt4_original_bert_multilingual_params_setC	human_dataset_externo	2766	234	3000	Label 0	92,20%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	llama_8b	219	1901	2120	Label 1	89,67%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	llama_8b_finetuned	2	980	982	Label 1	99,80%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	gpt4_finetuned	58	2942	3000	Label 1	98,07%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	gpt4_finetuned_validation	19	1481	1500	Label 1	98,73%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	gpt4	238	1762	2000	Label 1	88,10%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	human_original	3991	13482	17473	Label 0	22,84%
llama8b_bert_multilingual_params_setA	human_dataset_externo	603	2397	3000	Label 0	20,10%